

Title: Language Policy and Borrowing: A Multifaceted Relationship

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Introduction

Language policy plays a pivotal role in shaping the linguistic landscape of a nation or region. It encompasses decisions and strategies governments or language authorities formulate to regulate, promote, or protect languages within their jurisdiction. Language borrowing, on the other hand, is a dynamic process where languages interact, leading to the exchange of vocabulary, structures, and linguistic elements. This article explores the intricate relationship between language policy and borrowing, highlighting how language policies can either facilitate or hinder the borrowing process and impact linguistic diversity.

The Dynamics of Language Borrowing

Language borrowing is a natural consequence of language contact, occurring when speakers of different languages interact. This interaction can take various forms, including trade, migration, colonization, or cultural exchange. As a result, languages influence one another, leading to the incorporation of foreign words and

